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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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INTEGRATING VISUAL-BASED ACTIVITIES IN ENGLISH LESSONS FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS

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Abstract: This research investigates the incorporation of visual-based activities in basic English courses and their effect on young learners' language acquisition. Visual activities such as flashcards, images, storyboards, and interactive videos enhance comprehension, retention, and engagement. The study integrates theoretical frameworks with empirical classroom observations of 40 students aged 7-10 in the Tashkent region. Data collection comprised pre- and post-tests, observation notes, and teacher interviews. The results demonstrate that visually centred activities significantly improve vocabulary acquisition, student motivation, and classroom engagement. The study concludes that incorporating visual activities is essential for effective and interactive English language teaching in primary education.

Key words: Visual activities, elementary education, EFL learners, vocabulary development, motivation, classroom interaction, teaching strategies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot boshlang'ich sinf ingliz tili darslarida vizual asoslangan faoliyatlarni integratsiya qilish va ularning o'quvchilarning tilni o'zlashtirishiga ta'sirini o'rganadi. Flesh-kartlar, rasmlar, hikoya doskalari va interaktiv videolar tushunish, eslab qolish hamda faollikni oshiradi. Tadqiqot nazariy yondashuvlar hamda Toshkent viloyatidagi 7-10 yoshli 40 nafar o'quvchi ishtirokidagi amaliy kuzatuvlarni birlashtirdi. Ma'lumotlar oldindan va keyin o'tkazilgan testlar, kuzatuv qaydlari hamda o'qituvchilar bilan o'tkazilgan intervyular orqali to'plandi. Natijalar vizual faoliyatlar so'z boyligini oshirish, motivatsiya va sinfdagi muloqotni sezilarli darajada yaxshilashini ko'rsatdi. Tadqiqot yakunida vizual asoslangan faoliyatlarni dars jarayoniga integratsiya qilish boshlang'ich ta'limda samarali va interaktiv ingliz tili o'qitish uchun zarur ekanligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Vizual faoliyatlar, boshlang'ich ta'lim, EFL o'quvchilari, so'z boyligini rivojlantirish, motivatsiya, sinfdagi muloqot, o'qitish strategiyalari.

Аннотация: Данное исследование рассматривает интеграцию визуальных активностей в уроках английского языка в начальной школе и их влияние на усвоение языка младшими школьниками. Карточки, изображения, сториборды и интерактивные видео способствуют пониманию, запоминанию и активности учащихся. Исследование сочетало теоретические основы с практическими наблюдениями в классе с участием 40 учеников в возрасте 7-10 лет в Ташкентской области. Данные собирались посредством тестов до и после занятий, наблюдений и интервью с учителями. Результаты показали, что визуальные активности значительно улучшают усвоение словарного запаса, мотивацию и взаимодействие в классе. В заключение подчёркивается, что интеграция визуальных активностей необходима для эффективного и интерактивного обучения английскому языку в начальной школе.

Ключевые слова: Визуальные активности, начальное образование, учащиеся EFL, развитие словарного запаса, мотивация, взаимодействие в классе, стратегии преподавания.

INTRODUCTION

To teach English effectively to elementary school students, it is essential to create learning situations that are dynamic, engaging, and meaningful. Visual-based exercises can achieve this by making vocabulary, grammar, and communication tasks more concrete and interactive (Harmer, 2015, p. 66). Paivio's Dual Coding Theory (1986, p. 55) and Mayer's Multimedia Learning Theory (2009, p. 63) support the idea that integrating visual and verbal information enhances retention and comprehension. In Uzbekistan, the elementary school curriculum favors interactive and communicative approaches; however, many classes still rely on conventional textbook-based activities (Usmonova, 2020, p. 89). This study examines the impact of incorporating visu-

al-based activities into English lessons on vocabulary acquisition, student motivation, and classroom interaction among learners aged 7-10. The goals of the study are to determine how visual activities influence vocabulary development, to analyze students' levels of interest and motivation, and to provide practical recommendations for integrating visual-based activities into elementary English instruction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Constructivist and cognitive theories emphasize active, multisensory learning (Piaget, 1952, p. 41; Vygotsky, 1978, p. 86). Within the framework of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), visual activities function as scaffolding by helping learners understand abstract concepts through concrete representation. Mayer (2009, p. 63) argues that students retain information more effectively when auditory and visual inputs are presented simultaneously. Bruner (1996, p. 78) highlights that young learners rely heavily on sensory perception; therefore, visual exercises enhance both comprehension and engagement. Research indicates that visual activities such as flashcards, storyboards, illustrated books, and interactive videos improve vocabulary retention and learner motivation (Wright, 2010, p. 57; Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2013, p. 112). Harmer (2015, p. 65) maintains that such activities encourage active participation, collaboration, and communicative practice. Karimova (2022, p. 49) found that visual-based activities significantly improved both linguistic and cultural learning outcomes in English classes in Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research methods to provide a comprehensive analysis of the effects of visual-based activities on vocabulary acquisition and classroom engagement. The quantitative component utilized pre- and post-tests to measure students' vocabulary performance, while the qualitative component involved classroom observations and teacher interviews to gain deeper insight into learning processes and classroom dynamics. This methodological integration enabled both statistical analysis and an in-depth understanding of the factors influencing student engagement and learning outcomes. The study involved 40 public primary school students aged 7-10 years. The participants were randomly assigned to two groups: Experimental Group (n=20), whose students were taught using visual-based activities such as flashcards, storyboards, picture description tasks, and interactive video exercises.

Each lesson incorporated visual aids to facilitate vocabulary acquisition and sustain learner engagement; Control Group (n=20), whose students received traditional textbook-based instruction, including reading passages, writing exercises, and grammar-focused tasks without visual support. Both groups were matched in terms of age and language proficiency to ensure comparability and to provide a fair assessment of the effectiveness of visual-based activities compared to conventional methods. The intervention lasted four weeks, with three lessons per week. Each session in the experimental group included interactive and visually supported tasks designed to promote vocabulary acquisition and active participation. These activities included flashcard games, where students associated words with images to strengthen memory retention; storyboard storytelling, in which learners created stories using pictures to practice vocabulary and sentence construction; picture description tasks aimed at developing speaking and comprehension skills; and interactive video activities presenting new vocabulary in contextualized short clips followed by discussion and follow-up exercises. Data were collected through three primary instruments: vocabulary tests administered before and after the intervention to measure vocabulary growth; classroom observation protocols documenting levels of participation, attention, and engagement; and semi-structured teacher interviews exploring perceptions of student motivation, comprehension, and interaction.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

We employed both quantitative and qualitative methodologies to analyze the collected data. Quantitative data were examined using descriptive statistics to compare the pre- and post-test results of both groups. The mean scores for each test were calculated, and percentage gains were compared to evaluate the effectiveness of visual-based activities in facilitating vocabulary acquisition. Qualitative data, derived from classroom observation notes and teacher interview responses, were coded thematically. This process involved identifying recurring themes and patterns related to motivation, comprehension, and student interaction. These findings provided valuable insights into how visually centered activities influenced student engagement and learning outcomes. The mixed-methods approach enabled a comprehensive evaluation of the effectiveness of visual-based activities in enhancing vocabulary learning and promoting active classroom participation.

Table 1: Pre- and Post-test scores

Group	Pre-test Mean (%)	Post-test Mean (%)	Improvement (%)
Experimental (Visual Activities)	56.8	87.5	30.7
Control (Traditional)	57.2	70.5	13.3

The vocabulary test results indicate that the experimental group, which was instructed through visual activities, demonstrated substantially higher performance, achieving a 30.7% improvement in vocabulary acquisition. In contrast, the control group, which received traditional textbook-based instruction, showed only a 13.3% improvement. These findings unequivocally substantiate the claim that visual-based exercises significantly enhance vocabulary acquisition. The results corroborate Mayer's (2009, p. 63) assertion that integrating visual and verbal information improves retention and comprehension and align with Arslan and Saka's (2021, p. 22) findings, which highlight the considerable advantages of visual materials for young learners.

Table 2: Teacher observations

Theme	Description	Example Quotation
Motivation	High engagement and enthusiasm	"Students eagerly participate in flashcard and storyboard activities."
Comprehension	Faster understanding of words and sentences	"Visual activities make meanings clearer than verbal explanation alone."
Interaction	Encourages speaking and collaboration	"Children describe pictures and videos in groups, improving confidence."
Challenges	Preparation and resource availability	"Finding and preparing suitable visuals for every topic takes time."

Qualitative data from teacher observations further revealed that the implementation of visual activities increased student motivation, improved comprehension, and enhanced classroom engagement. Teachers reported heightened enthusiasm and active participation during activities such as flashcards and storyboards. They observed that students grasped vocabulary and sentence structures more rapidly when supported by visuals or videos compared to exclusively verbal explanations. This suggests that visual exercises are particularly effective in strengthening comprehension. Additionally, the participatory nature of visual-based activities encouraged peer interaction and speaking practice, thereby increasing students' confidence. However, instructors also reported challenges, particularly the time required for preparation and the limited availability of high-quality visual resources. These findings are consistent with Richards and Rodgers (2014, p. 88), who emphasize the importance of visual aids in enhancing motivation and comprehension while acknowledging potential practical constraints.

Activities incorporating visual elements significantly contributed to vocabulary acquisition and classroom engagement. The integration of visual aids, including flashcards, videos, and realia, into English lessons was found to improve vocabulary retention and increase student involvement. This aligns with Paivio's (1986) Dual Coding Theory, which posits that learning is enhanced when verbal and visual information are processed through dual cognitive channels. Mayer's Multimedia Learning Theory (2009) further supports this perspective, suggesting that learning is optimized when information is presented through both visual and auditory modalities, facilitating deeper cognitive processing and more efficient knowledge retrieval. The experimental group exposed to visual exercises demonstrated higher levels of motivation, engagement, and vocabulary retention compared to the control group relying on traditional textbooks. This finding corresponds with Dörnyei and Ushioda's (2013, p. 112) emphasis on the central role of motivation and engagement in second language acquisition. Students participating in visually enriched sessions exhibited greater enthusiasm and sustained attention, which positively influenced their ability to learn and recall new terminology.

Nevertheless, teachers identified preparation time and limited resource availability as significant constraints. Although visual aids proved highly effective, instructors experienced difficulty locating appropriate materials and dedicating sufficient time for lesson preparation. These challenges are consistent with Karimova's (2022, p. 51) findings, which indicate that adequate resources and preparation time are critical factors for the effective implementation of visual aids in classroom settings. Despite these limitations, instructors agreed that the pedagogical benefits of visual aids, particularly in creating a dynamic and engaging learning environment, outweighed the practical challenges.

CONCLUSION

Integrating visual activities into elementary English lessons enhances vocabulary acquisition, sustains learners' interest, and strengthens peer interaction. Teachers are encouraged to incorporate flashcards, storyboards, picture books, and films that actively engage students in the learning process. Schools should support this approach by providing adequate instructional resources and offering professional development for teachers to maximize the effectiveness of visual materials. Future research may explore the potential of digital technologies, such as augmented reality and interactive whiteboards, to further enhance and complement visual learning in primary education.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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